

Catalytic pyrolysis of wood blended with ZSM-5 catalyst

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Abstract : In the order to improve the quality of biomass pyrolysis and its bio-oil, mesoporous ZSM-5 was mixed with Yunnan pine for the catalytic pyrolysis in a fixed reactor. The compositions of bio-oil were analyzed by Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS). The results of XRD, N₂ absorption/desorption isotherm and TEM indicated the presence of mesopores within ZSM-5. The result of catalytic pyrolysis showed that with the increase of catalyst/biomass ratio, the content of char and gaseous products increases and the content of bio-oil decreases. At the same time, the phenolics, aldehydes, ketones, organic acids and furans in bio-oil decrease distinctly while desirable hydrocarbons increase drastically from 1.11 to 72.07 wt%.

Keywords : Mesoporous ZSM-5, Yunnan pine, pyrolysis, hydrocarbons.

Introduction

Facing the severe environmental and energy situation resulting from the excessive consumption of fossil energy, people have to explore different ways of using biomass with emphasis on cleanliness and renewability. Among technologies of biomass utilization, pyrolysis is considered the most promising way¹. In the temperature range from 350 to 700 °C, biomass can be converted into bio-oil, char and gaseous products in the absence of air or oxygen.

Bio-oil is a valuable liquid consisting primarily of phenolic compounds, as well as aldehydes, ketones, alcohols, organic acids and esters². Compared to the diesel, the bio-oil possesses characteristics of high viscosity, density and low gross heating value because of the high content of oxygenated compounds³. Catalysts could upgrade bio-oil by removing the oxygen and thus increase the gross heating value and stability of bio-oil. At present, zeolite molecular sieves and mesoporous molecular sieves are frequently applied for the catalytic reform of bio-oil. The research of Nguyen *et al.*⁴ of the pine catalytic pyrolysis Na_{0.2}H_{0.8}-FAU showed the excellent characteristic of deoxidation to reduce the contents of organic acids, aldehydes and ketones. The results of Wang *et al.*⁵ show that

the presence of ZSM-5 increases the aromatics dramatically and depending on the catalytic condition the content of aromatics reaches 15 to 92.6 wt%. Adam *et al.*⁶ studied the catalytic pyrolysis using Al-MCM-41, modified Al-MCM-41, SBA-15 and Al/SBA-15, and found that Al-MCM-41 increased the yields of acetic acid and furan at the cost of high-weight phenolic compounds. Lu *et al.*⁷ compared the performance of zeolite molecular sieves and mesoporous molecular sieves for upgrading bio-oil, and the results indicated that zeolite molecular sieves (HZSM-5, HY) preferentially yielded hydrocarbons, while mesoporous molecular sieves (ZrO₂, TiO₂, SBA-15 and Al/SBA-15) yielded more furan, furfural and acetic acid. So far, mesoporous ZSM-5 is considered the best catalyst for the production of aromatics. However, the micropores of ZSM-5 not only restrict the diffusion of large molecules, but also reduce the rate of transport of reactants and products in the micropores. In this paper, ZSM-5 was used for upgrading bio-oil and the influence of catalyst/biomass ratio on bio-oil was also studied.

Experimental method

Materials :

Yunnan pine was purchased from Pu'er city in Yunnan

province. Before the experiment, Yunnan pine were ground in a high-speed rotary cutting mill and sieved to a particle size in the 0.250–0.420 mm range. The feedstock was dried at 105 ± 2 °C for 24 h, and then sealed in bags.

Mesoporous ZSM-5 with white bar structure was provided from the Catalyst Plant of Nankai University. The Si/Al ratio of ZSM-5 is about 25. The chemical composition of catalysts is as follows : Al_2O_3 , 5–5.5 wt%; SiO_2 , 80–85 wt%. The absorption capacities of hexane, cyclohexane and water are 9.5–10.5 wt%, 2.0–2.5 wt% and 11.0–12.0 wt%, respectively. Before the experiment, the bare ZSM-5 was ground manually in a mortar and sieved for 0.185–0.250 mm. After that mesoporous ZSM-5 was dried at 105 ± 2 °C for 24 h and then sealed for the experiment.

Tetrahydrofuran, AR, was provided from Zhiyuan Chemical Reagent Company in Tianjin. High purity nitrogen was provided by Yunnan Copper.

Experiment

Characterization of catalyst :

The X-ray Powder Diffraction (XRD) and N_2 absorption/desorption were used for characterization analysis of mesoporous ZSM-5. The spectra of X-ray diffractometer

(TTR III) were scanned at a rate of 10.0 °C min^{-1} in the range $2\theta = 5.0^\circ$ – 90.0° . The textural parameters were analyzed by N_2 absorption/desorption isotherm with TriStar II 3020 at -195.85 °C. Before measurement catalyst was degassed under vacuum at 300 °C for 10 h. The BET surface area was calculated from the linear portion of BET plot. The micropore volume and external surface areas were calculated by t-plot method while the pore size distribution was determined by the BJH model. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were taken by JEM-2100 at 200 kV for 0.5 h.

Catalytic pyrolysis with fixed-bed reactor :

The fixed-bed reactor for pyrolysis of our design with programmed temperature control was used. The schematic diagram of fixed-bed is explained in Fig. 1. Firstly, the dry glass fiber was inserted into installed vertically reactor for loading feedstock. The mixture of Yunnan pine and mesoporous ZSM-5 was then added to the reactor. The bottom of reactor was linked with the high purity nitrogen while the top of reactor was connected with the condenser. The distance from reaction part to the condensation pipe was 60 cm long and the transmission pipe was heated and held at 500 °C. Prior to the experiment, the

(1) Nitrogen cylinder, (2) Flowmeter, (3) Pyrolysis reactor, (4) Electrical furnace, (5) Temperature controller, (6) Cooling coil, (7) Outfall, (8) Infall, (9) Receiving flask, (10) Ice water, (11-12) End gas absorber.

Fig. 1. Diagram of fixed-bed apparatus.

high purity nitrogen was swept for 5 min and then the reactor was heated rapidly to the specific temperatures with a heating rate of 250 °C min⁻¹ rapidly. Afterwards, the temperature of reactor stayed the same for 25 min.

After pyrolysis, the obtained bio-oil was dissolved in tetrahydrofuran. Tetrahydrofuran and mixture were both weighed, and the yield of bio-oil was calculated by the difference. The weight of catalysts is subtracted from the total weight of char and catalysts after the pyrolysis to get the yield of bio-char and coke deposited on catalysts. The difference amounted to the yield in gaseous products.

Chemical analysis of bio-oil :

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometer (GC-MS) analysis of bio-oil was performed on an ITQ 900 which is made by Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA, using capillary chromatographic column : HP-5MS (30 m × 0.25 mm × 0.25 μm). Temperature of the injector was 280 °C; the split ratio of the carrier gas was 1 : 10 using high purity helium. Oven temperature was at first held at 50 °C for 5

min, and then the temperature was ramped from 50 to 280 °C at 5 °C min⁻¹, and held for 5 min. For the MS condition, Ionization methods : EI; Ionization energy : 70 eV; The scan per second over range electron (*m/z*) : 30–500 amu; Ion source temperature : 230 °C.

Results and discussion

Physical characteristics of catalyst :

Fig. 2 shows the XRD pattern of the catalyst. The two strong diffraction peaks at 8° and 23° showed the characteristic structure of MFI zeolite^{8,9}. Table 1 shows the textural properties of ZSM-5. The results indicate that ZSM-5 possesses the high mesopore volume of 0.113 mL/g which was calculated by the difference. Fig. 3 shows the N₂ absorption/desorption isotherm curves of ZSM-5, and the type of IV with apparent H1 hysteresis is the evidence of the presence of a well-defined mesoporous structure¹⁰. Fig. 3 also displays the pore size distribution of ZSM-5 evaluated by BJH method. The transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images shown in Fig. 4 dem-

Fig. 2. XRD patterns of ZSM-5.

Fig. 3. N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherm curves and pore size distribution of ZSM-5.

onstrate the presence of disordered mesopores within the ZSM-5 crystals. This closely conforms with the results of N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherm curves.

The yield of products :

Pyrolysis and catalytic pyrolysis were carried out at 500 °C with nitrogen flow rate of 200 mL min⁻¹. The yields of products from biomass through catalytic pyrolysis are shown in Fig. 5. The results show that in the presence of mesoporous ZSM-5, the yield of bio-oil decreases while both the yields of char/coke and gaseous products increase. The results are similar to the relevant

researches¹¹. Moreover, the increase of ratio of ZSM-5/biomass results in the significant decrease of bio-oil from 35 to 18 wt%, and with an increase of gaseous products from 34.5 to 47 wt% combined with a slight increase of bio-char. The high-molecular compounds could be cracked by mesoporous ZSM-5 with high catalytic activity and converted into light compounds, and thus increase the content of gaseous products and decrease the content of bio-oil. During catalytic reaction repolymerization of high-molecular also takes place on catalysts to form the coke.

Products selectivity :

Table 1. The textural properties of catalyst

Sample	S _{BET} (m ² /g) ^a	S _{micro} (m ² /g) ^b	S _{ext} (m ² /g) ^b	V _{total} (mL/g) ^c	V _{meso} (mL/g) ^d	V _{micro} (mL/g) ^b	D _{pore size} (nm) ^e
ZSM-5	210.95	136.63	74.32	0.176	0.113	0.063	3.33

^aFrom N₂ adsorption measurement (BET method). ^bFrom N₂ adsorption measurement (t-plot method). ^cP/P₀ = 0.96. ^dBy difference. ^eFrom BET method.

Fig. 4. Transmission electron micrographs of mesoporous ZSM-5.

Fig. 5. The influence of catalysts/biomass ratio on yields of products.

The bio-oil from Yunnan pine through pyrolysis and catalytic pyrolysis are detected by GC-MS. The total ion chromatograms of bio-oil through pyrolysis and catalytic pyrolysis with 5 : 1 of catalyst/biomass ratio are shown in Fig. 6. The detailed list of chemical compounds of various bio-oil is presented in Table 2. The results show that

crude bio-oil mainly contains phenolics, aldehydes, ketones, organic acids, furans, hydrocarbons, with phenolics as the major component with 59.19 wt% arising mainly from the pyrolysis of lignin. Besides, there are also large numbers of unidentified components, mainly high-weight oxygenated compounds in bio-oil. In the bio-oil the fourth

Fig. 6. The total ion chromatogram of crude bio-oil (A) and upgrading bio-oil (B) when the catalysts/biomass ratio was 5 : 1.

Table 2. Relative contents of compounds in bio-oil (wt%)

RT (min)	Compound	Formula	Crude bio-oil	Catalysts/Biomass ratio			
				1 : 1	2 : 1	3 : 1	5 : 1
	Phenolics		59.19	51.30	42.79	45.14	27.93
4.94	Pyrogallol	C ₆ H ₆ O ₃	-	-	-	-	-
8.04	Phenol	C ₆ H ₆ O	0.42	0.74	1.11	0.76	-
10.08	2-Methylphenol	C ₇ H ₈ O	0.36	0.44	0.57	-	-
10.70	4-Methylphenol	C ₇ H ₈ O	0.66	1.19	1.29	-	-
10.99	Guaiacol	C ₇ H ₈ O ₂	4.14	4.01	3.58	1.84	-
11.50	2,5-Dimethylphenol	C ₈ H ₁₀ O	0.26	0.57	-	-	-
12.79	3,5-Dimethylphenol	C ₈ H ₁₀ O	0.77	-	-	-	-
13.39	2,3-Dimethylphenol	C ₈ H ₁₀ O	0.28	-	-	-	-
13.54	4-Methylguaiacol	C ₈ H ₁₀ O ₂	0.41	0.32	-	-	-
13.78	4-Ethylresorcinol	C ₈ H ₁₀ O ₂	0.30	-	-	-	-

Table-2 (contd.)

13.97	2-Hydroxy-4-methylanisole	C ₈ H ₁₀ O ₂	6.61	6.33	7.03	4.40	-
14.51	Pyrocatechol	C ₆ H ₆ O ₂	2.79	1.77	-	-	-
15.25	3,4-Dimethoxytoluene	C ₉ H ₁₂ O ₂	0.93	-	-	-	-
15.99	3-Methoxy-2-benzenediol	C ₇ H ₈ O ₃	0.31	-	-	-	-
16.12	3-Methylcatechol	C ₇ H ₈ O ₂	0.65	-	-	-	-
16.37	4-Ethylguaiaicol	C ₉ H ₁₂ O ₂	2.80	3.15	2.95	16.93	-
17.22	3-Methylcatechol	C ₇ H ₈ O ₂	0.36	-	-	0.92	-
17.34	2-Methoxy-4-vinylphenol	C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂	5.90	6.01	6.47	3.87	-
17.05	4-Methylcatechol	C ₇ H ₈ O ₂	5.58	-	-	-	-
17.55	1,2-Dimethoxy-4-ethylbenzene	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O ₂	0.92	-	-	-	-
18.34	2,6-Dimethoxyphenol	C ₈ H ₁₀ O ₃	0.94	0.72	-	-	-
18.46	3-Allylguaiacol	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂	1.38	1.77	1.97	-	-
18.52	2-Methoxy-6-(1-propenyl)phenol	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂	-	-	-	1.57	-
18.72	Dihydroeugenol	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O ₂	0.76	1.12	1.06	-	-
19.49	2,5-Dimethylhydroquinone	C ₈ H ₁₀ O ₂	0.36	-	-	-	-
19.77	2-Methoxy-5-[(E)-1-propenyl]phenol	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂	-	1.99	-	-	-
19.81	Isoeugenol	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂	0.92	-	-	-	-
20.87	(E)-2-Methoxy-4-(prop-1-enyl)phenol	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂	7.73	6.98	6.11	3.42	-
21.16	1-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-1-propanol	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O ₂	0.62	0.79	-	-	-
21.85	Tert-butylhydroquinone	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O ₂	1.20	1.22	-	-	-
22.35	2,6-Di-tert-butyl-4-methylphenol	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	2.29	4.03	7.77	11.42	27.93
22.73	5-Tert-butylpyrogallol	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O ₃	0.49	0.83	-	-	-
22.88	Dihydroeugenol	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O ₂	1.45	1.66	1.06	-	-
23.69	3-Tert-butyl-4-hydroxyanisole	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ O ₂	1.53	0.85	0.68	-	-
23.92	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxycinnamyl alcohol	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₃	0.56	0.66	-	-	-
24.15	1,2-Dimethoxy-4-n-propylbenzene	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ O ₂	0.51	0.72	-	-	-
25.64	Vanillyl ethyl ether	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O ₃	1.51	1.71	-	-	-
26.76	4-Allyl-2,6-dimethoxyphenol	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₃	1.30	1.21	1.12	-	-
35.75	7β-Hydroxytotarol	C ₂₀ H ₃₀ O ₂	1.20	0.53	-	-	-
	Aldehydes		3.18				
4.26	3-Furaldehyde	C ₅ H ₄ O ₂	1.70	-	-	-	-
19.66	Isovanillin	C ₈ H ₈ O ₃	0.84	-	-	-	-
23.26	D-Talose	C ₆ H ₁₂ O ₆	0.64	-	-	-	-
	Ketones		1.45	0.63			
6.39	Cyclohexanone	C ₆ H ₁₀ O	0.51	0.32	-	-	-
5.89	2-Methyl-2-cyclopentenone	C ₆ H ₈ O	0.19	-	-	-	-
9.21	Methyl cyclopentenone	C ₆ H ₈ O ₂	0.57	0.31	-	-	-
27.54	Acetosyringone	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₄	0.18	-	-	-	-
	Acids		1.62	1.07			
6.12	3-Butenoic acid	C ₄ H ₄ O ₂	0.45	-	-	-	-
8.37	Oxaceprol	C ₇ H ₁₁ NO ₄	0.45	0.41	-	-	-
9.64	3-Methylsalicylic acid	C ₈ H ₈ O ₃	0.15	0.34	-	-	-
24.55	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxycinnamic acid	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₄	0.25	0.32	-	-	-
26.64	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenylpyruvic acid	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₅	0.31	-	-	-	-
	Furans		1.15	1.26	0.70		
4.28	2,5-Dimethylfuran	C ₆ H ₈ O	-	0.93	0.70	-	-

Table-2 (contd.)

4.75	Furfuryl alcohol	C ₅ H ₆ O ₂	0.58	–	–	–	–
7.40	5-Methyl furfural	C ₆ H ₆ O ₂	0.57	0.33	–	–	–
	Hydrocarbon compound		1.11	19.61	45.91	50.52	72.07
12.66	3-Methylindene	C ₁₀ H ₁₀	–	0.54	0.94	0.93	–
12.84	2-Methylindene	C ₁₀ H ₁₀	–	1.75	2.07	1.63	1.83
13.66	Naphthalene	C ₁₀ H ₈	–	4.95	11.59	9.66	13.28
15.81	1,2-Dihydro-6-methylnaphthalene	C ₁₁ H ₁₂	–	0.89	1.54	1.57	1.76
16.76	1,6-Methano[10]annulene	C ₁₁ H ₁₀	–	6.27	19.76	24.40	35.66
17.89	1,1,6-Trimethyltetralin	C ₁₃ H ₁₈	–	–	–	0.69	–
19.39	2-Ethyl-naphthalene	C ₁₂ H ₁₂	–	–	–	0.94	1.74
19.8	1,4,5-Trimethyl-5,6-dihydronaphthalene	C ₁₃ H ₁₆	–	–	2.41	–	–
19.67	1,7-Dimethylnaphthalene	C ₁₂ H ₁₂	–	2.76	6.45	7.43	17.81
21.57	1-Ethyl-2,3,5,6-tetramethylbenzene	C ₁₂ H ₁₈	0.40	1.46	–	–	–
26.26	γ-Selinene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	0.18	–	–	–	–
28.31	1,1-Diphenyl-3-methylbutane	C ₁₇ H ₂₀	0.52	0.99	–	–	–
28.69	Phenanthrene	C ₁₄ H ₁₀	–	–	1.15	0.82	–
31.18	Dodecahydrotriphenylene	C ₁₈ H ₂₄	–	–	–	1.35	–
31.21	4-Methylphenanthrene	C ₁₅ H ₁₂	–	–	–	1.11	–
	Unidentified compounds		32.31	26.14	10.62	4.34	–

highest compounds (*E*)-2-methoxy-4-(prop-1-enyl)phenol, 2-hydroxy-4-methylanisole, 2-methoxy-4-vinylphenol and guaiacol respectively account for 7.73 wt%, 6.61 wt%, 5.90 wt% and 4.14 wt%.

Fig. 7 shows the selectivity of catalyst/biomass ratio for various compounds. In the presence of ZSM-5, the phenolics, aldehydes, ketones, acids, furans as well as oxygenated unidentified compounds decrease while the

Fig. 7. The selectivity of various catalysts/biomass ratios for different compounds.

hydrocarbons increase drastically. During catalytic pyrolysis, ZSM-5 showed high activity of deoxygenation and aromatization. In the research of Carlson *et al.*¹² ZSM-5, silicalite, beta, γ -zeolite and silica-alumina were used for the catalytic fast pyrolysis of biomass, and the results indicated that high product selectivity of ZSM-5 is attributed to both the size of the catalyst pores and the nature of the active sites. As catalyst/biomass ratio increases from 1 : 1 to 5 : 1, the aldehydes, ketones, organic acids and furans in bio-oil are gradually reduced to zero. The content of phenolics is reduced from 59.19 to 27.93%, while the desirable hydrocarbons increase greatly from 1.11 to 72.07%. The hydrocarbons mainly include 1,6-methano[10]annulene and aromatics such as 1,7-dimethylnaphthalene and naphthalene. Olefins and aromatics that possess high chemical stability and characteristic of combustion could be mixed with present petrol and diesel for burning. High catalyst/biomass ratio promotes fully catalytic reactions and thus increases the content of hydrocarbons at the cost of oxygenated compounds.

Conclusion

(i) The results of XRD, N₂ absorption/desorption isotherm and TEM showed that the ZSM-5 possesses the

apparent characteristic structure of MFI zeolite and the high mesoporous volume with the average pore size 3.33 nm.

(ii) With the increase of catalyst/biomass ratio, the content of char and gaseous products increases and bio-oil decreases due to the full catalysis. The mesoporous ZSM-5 has an important influence on upgrading bio-oil by deoxygenation and aromatization. The increase of catalyst/biomass ratio results in the remarkable change of bio-oil : the phenolics, aldehydes, ketones, organic acids, furans in bio-oil decrease distinctly while desirable hydrocarbons increase drastically from 1.11 to 72.07%.

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